

HOW TRADE OPENNESS SHAPES UNEMPLOYMENT IN DEVELOPING ECONOMIES: A DYNAMIC PANEL DATA APPROACH

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Abstract

This study employs dynamic panel data modelling to analyse trade openness and unemployment in 54 upper-middle-income countries from 1991 to 2023. This study employs macroeconomic control variables, including inflation, FDI, and real GDP, to examine unemployment dynamics. The study's results demonstrate that trade openness, FDI, and real GDP can reduce unemployment both in the short term and the long term. While increasing inflation can lead to increased unemployment in the short and long term. This study then analyses the average annual unemployment convergence rate. This study's findings emphasise that the government must encourage trade liberalisation policies and maintain macroeconomic stability to reduce unemployment.

Keywords: Trade Openness; Unemployment; Dynamic Panel Data; System Gmm; Inflation; Foreign Direct Investment; Economic Growth.

JEL Classification Codes: E24, E31, F16, F43, F21.

1. INTRODUCTION

From the perspective of job seekers, people who lose their jobs typically do not immediately find new employment. Because people who lose their jobs may wait for the right job opportunity, take additional training and education, or become desperate and temporarily stop looking for work. Meanwhile, from the company's perspective, reducing its workforce during a recession can enable it to recover more quickly later. Then, unemployment will not occur immediately because the company needs time to ensure stable economic conditions before opening new job vacancies. This dynamic lag effect is crucial for understanding the tension, as job seekers require time to re-enter the labor market. Some unemployed people may become desperate after losing their jobs and delay entering the workforce. Therefore, to analyze the reduction, a dynamic perspective is needed using Dynamic Panel Data (DPD) modeling for more accurate unemployment analysis results (Guliyev, 2023).

The theory of comparative advantage, as developed in the Ricardian and Heckscher-Ohlin models, posits that countries tend to specialise in producing goods where they have a cost advantage. Trade openness plays a critical role in this process, as it facilitates the reallocation of labour to more productive and competitive sectors, thus preventing labour from becoming stuck in inefficient industries and reducing structural unemployment. Empirical evidence supports this theory, showing that trade openness negatively correlates with unemployment in the long run, particularly in labour-intensive countries (Dutt et al., 2009).

Trade openness is essential in global trade because it allocates labor to industries where it has a comparative advantage. Thus, preventing labor from working in uncompetitive industries and

shifting to competitive industries to reduce structural unemployment. Empirical evidence also supports this theory of international trade, which shows that trade openness can reduce unemployment in the long term, especially in labor-intensive countries (Dutt et al., 2009).

Trade openness is typically measured by the ratio of a country's exports and imports to its GDP. Trade openness is a key factor in reducing unemployment rates in developing countries. From the export side, it will increase demand for goods and services from abroad, encouraging domestic companies to increase production and employment. On the import side, access to quality and cheap goods inputs and sophisticated technology will increase production efficiency, reduce costs, and encourage business expansion and job creation (Felbermayr et al., 2011). Additionally, FDI, real GDP, and trade openness were found to significantly reduce unemployment in the long term (Alfalih, 2024). Because trade openness is helpful for job growth in developing countries (Demiral et al., 2020). Then, increasing exports can also contribute to reducing the unemployment rate. (Gonese et al., 2023). Other empirical findings also confirm that increasing trade openness can reduce unemployment, while decreasing openness can increase unemployment (Abdul-Mumuni et al., 2023). Then, for low-income countries, trade openness has also been shown to reduce unemployment in the long term (S. Ali et al., 2022).

Trade liberalization can reduce unemployment by expanding market access to international markets, encouraging production through exports, and creating new job opportunities. The impact of trade liberalization is more effective in countries with flexible labor markets, with many job opportunities that are easy to get (Stepanok, 2018). Reducing restrictions on trade liberalization will reduce unemployment in countries with open trade policies with other countries (Boulhol, 2011). Trade liberalization also reduces unemployment in urban areas with flexible labor markets and strong export industries. (Hasan et al., 2012). Workers in export-oriented industries benefit most from trade liberalisation due to their lower risk of job loss (Ranjan, 2012). However, poorly implemented export tariffs may compromise urban institutional resilience (Güven, 2024). While trade openness generates job opportunities, its benefits depend significantly on national economic conditions and the capacity to raise household incomes (Bhat & Beg, 2023).

Open markets attract FDI, as trade liberalisation facilitates cross-border investment and deeper economic integration. FDI supports job creation through the establishment of multinational enterprises. In the long run, trade openness and FDI significantly affect unemployment, especially among youth (Liu et al., 2022).

Higher GDP levels are typically associated with lower unemployment rates. Economic growth increases public consumption, prompting firms to hire more workers to meet the rising demand for their products and services. It also encourages domestic and foreign investment, creating new businesses and jobs. Thus, economic diversification becomes essential for sustaining growth, creating employment, and reducing unemployment (Alfalih, 2024). Countries with higher productivity also tend to experience lower unemployment (Epifani & Gancia, 2005). There is strong evidence that unemployment moves in tandem with economic activity: as growth accelerates, employment increases, and as growth slows, unemployment rises (Aleksandravičienė et al., 2024).

According to the classical Phillips Curve framework, there is a short-run trade-off between inflation and unemployment. When aggregate demand rises, firms expand production and increase hiring, reducing unemployment, but this process also drives inflation due to limited capacity (Moridian et al., 2024). Central banks may tolerate higher inflation in response to economic shocks to avoid worsening unemployment (Lepetit, 2020). Inflation may sometimes reduce unemployment in the short term, mainly when it reflects strong domestic demand and active labour markets (Das, 1997;Karanassou & Sala, 2010). Prior studies also confirm a significant trade-off between unemployment and inflation (Ribba, 2022;Gabriel et al., 2022).

However, inflation can also lead to increased unemployment. As prices rise, workers may demand higher wages, which in turn raises firms' labour costs and potentially results in layoffs. Price increases can lead to stagflation, characterized by high inflation, stagnant economic growth, and unemployment. Then, to overcome inflation, the central bank raises interest rates, which reduces investment, slows economic development, and leads to increased unemployment. Additionally, prior study suggests that labor market expectations drive disinflation and can reduce unemployment, particularly in a tight labor market (Crump et al., 2024). Because the central bank's inflation targeting policy in recent decades has contributed to low inflation stability (Bhattarai, 2016).

Additionally, reducing trade costs can lower inflation, while export sector investment has been shown to reduce unemployment in low-inflation environments (Cacciatore & Ghironi, 2021)(Kee & Hoon, 2005). Furthermore, employment guarantee programs can promote full employment without triggering the traditional inflation-unemployment trade-off (Carnevali & Deleidi, 2023). Some findings suggest that disinflation under inflation-targeting regimes does not always involve the expected trade-off between inflation and unemployment (Ferreira de Mendonça, 2009).

This study presents a novel approach to the discourse on trade openness and unemployment, with a focus on a group of developing countries. This group has been underrepresented in the empirical literature on this topic. Unlike studies that focus on individual countries, this research encompasses 54 Upper Middle-Income Countries from 1991 to 2023, enabling a broader and more comparative perspective on labor market dynamics in transitional economies. The study aims to provide fresh insights into how trade openness affects inclusive employment creation and to serve as a foundation for evidence-based policymaking.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilizes panel data from 54 upper-middle-income countries spanning the period from 1991 to 2023. These countries include: Albania, Armenia, Belize, Brazil, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Equatorial Guinea, Georgia, Indonesia, Jamaica, Libya, Marshall Islands, Moldova, Namibia, Peru, Tonga, St. Lucia, Tuvalu, Ukraine, St. Vincent and the Grenadines, Serbia, North Macedonia, Mauritius, Mongolia, Malaysia, Kazakhstan, Iran, Grenada, Fiji, Ecuador, Cuba, Bosnia and Herzegovina, China, Azerbaijan, Algeria, Argentina, Botswana, Belarus, Colombia, Dominica, El Salvador, Gabon, Guatemala, Iraq, Kosovo, Maldives, Mexico, Montenegro, Paraguay, South Africa, Suriname, Thailand, Turkmenistan, and Turkey.

The model used in this study is a dynamic panel data regression model, which is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & Unemployment_{it} \\
 & = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 Unemployment_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 Trade\ Openness_{it} + \beta_3 Inflation_{it} + \beta_4 FDI_{it} \\
 & + \beta_5 \ln GDP_{it} \\
 & + \varepsilon_{it}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Variable description: Unemployment is the percentage of the unemployed workforce looking for work, referring to ILO estimates. Trade Openness is the exports and imports of goods and services as a percentage of GDP. Inflation is measured by the Consumer Price Index (CPI), which reflects the annual change in the cost of living. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) refers to the net inflow of foreign direct investment as a percentage of a country's GDP. Ln GDP is the natural logarithm of Gross Domestic Product based on constant 2015 prices in US dollars.

All variables are obtained from indicators available at the World Bank. Estimation is carried out using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) method for dynamic panel data, with two main approaches: First-Difference GMM (FD-GMM) and System GMM (SYS-GMM). The two-step GMM model is more efficient and produces robust standard errors in the presence of heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. (Roodman, 2009). There are three main criteria for selecting the best GMM model. First is instrument validity, which requires the instrumental variables to be uncorrelated with the error term. The second is estimator consistency, which can be tested using the autocorrelation function. Third, unbiasedness, which is assessed by comparing the estimators from the Fixed Effects Model (FEM) and the Common Effect Model (CEM) method.

Dynamic panel models must employ appropriate estimation methods due to the correlation between the lagged dependent variable and the error term (Baltagi & Baltagi, 2008). Estimation with Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) in such models can produce biased and inconsistent results. Two tests are conducted to test the validity and consistency of the instruments used in GMM estimation. First, the Sargan test tests the instrument's validity under over-identification conditions (the number of instruments exceeds the number of parameters). The null hypothesis states that the instrument used is valid, or uncorrelated with the error. Second, the Arellano-Bond test tests the presence or absence of serial autocorrelation in the residuals. This test focuses on second-order autocorrelation, with the null hypothesis that there is no serial autocorrelation.

Then, the researcher conducted an unbiasedness test. If the unemployment lag one coefficient value of the SYS-GMM or FD-GMM model falls between the unemployment lag one coefficient values of the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Common Effect Model (CEM) method, it meets the unbiasedness requirements. Furthermore, the researcher calculates the long-term equation coefficients model. In addition, the convergence speed of the dependent variable value (unemployment) across country panels is also calculated to measure how quickly the unemployment value approaches the long-term equilibrium point.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Model unbiasedness test

Variable	Fixed Effect Method	First Difference Generalised Method of Moments	System Generalised Method of Moments	Common Effect Method
Lag 1 of Unemployment	0.73510978	0.82307251	0.87258188	0.9621523

The table above shows that the estimated coefficient of lag one unemployment in Sys-GMM and FD-GMM is between the estimated coefficient values of lag one unemployment in the Fixed Effect Methods (FEM) and Common Effect Methods (CEM) models, thus fulfilling the unbiasedness test. However, the SYS-GMM method is generally more efficient than FD-GMM because it utilizes more moments (in levels and differences), resulting in smaller standard errors. Given that the data structure in this study consists of many individual units (54 countries) and a relatively shorter period (33 years), the SYS-GMM approach is considered more appropriate because it can overcome the weaknesses of instruments commonly used in panels with a shorter period.

Table 2: Short-run estimation regression results

Variables (Dependent Variable: Unemployment)	Coefficient (Standard Error)
Independent variables:	
Lag one unemployment	0.8725819*** (0.0131506)
Trade openness	-0.0285916*** (0.0016391)
Inflation	0.001457*** (0.0001408)
Foreign direct investment	-0.0451417*** (0.0037753)
In gross domestic product	-0.5371861*** (0.1091068)
Number of observations N = 54, t = 33	1248
Diagnostic test:	
Sargan test	40.40043 p > 1.0000
Arellano-bond test	-1.7956 p > 0.0726

*** Significant level at 1%.

In the short run, the effects of lagged unemployment (lag 1) and inflation on current unemployment are positive and statistically significant at the 1% level. This indicates that a 1% increase in unemployment in the previous period leads to a 0.87258197% increase in the current unemployment rate; similarly, a 1% rise in inflation results in a 0.001457% increase in the unemployment rate. In contrast, in the short run, the effects of trade openness, foreign direct

investment (FDI), and the natural logarithm of gross domestic product (GDP) on unemployment are negatively related and statistically significant at the 1% level. Specifically, a 1% increase in trade (export plus import) per GDP reduces unemployment by approximately 0.0285916%, a 1% increase in FDI per GDP reduces unemployment by about 0.0451417%, and a 1% increase in the real GDP growth leads to a 0.05371861% reduction in the unemployment rate. Based on diagnostic testing, the Sargan test yields a chi-square value of 40.40043 with a p-value of 1.0000, which is greater than 0.05. This indicates that the model is valid and satisfies the overidentifying restrictions. Furthermore, the Arellano-Bond test shows a z-statistic of -1.7956 with a p-value of 0.0726, which is also greater than 0.05, suggesting that the model is consistent.

Table 3: Long-run estimation regression results

Variables (Dependent Variable: Unemployment)	Coefficient (Standard Error)
Trade openness	-0.2243923*** (0.0257702)
Inflation	0.0114345*** (0.0019793)
Foreign direct investment	-0.3542802*** (0.0298493)
In gross domestic product	-4.215932*** (0.6611706)

***Significant level at 1%.

In the long run, the effects of trade openness, FDI, and the natural logarithm of Gross Domestic Product (ln GDP) on unemployment are adverse and statistically significant at the 1% level. This means that a 1% increase in trade (export plus import) as a percentage of GDP reduces unemployment by approximately 0.2243923%. Similarly, a 1% increase in Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) as a percentage of GDP results in a decrease in unemployment of approximately 0.3542802%. Furthermore, a 1% increase in real GDP growth reduces unemployment by approximately -4.215932%. Meanwhile, in the long run, inflation has a positive and statistically significant effect on unemployment at the 1% level. Then, a 1% increase in the CPI inflation rate leads to a 0.0114345% increase in unemployment.

Table 4: Calculating unemployment convergence speed

Name	Value
Unemployment convergence speed	0.13629878

The convergence analysis concludes that unemployment is expected to decline over time, with an average annual adjustment speed of approximately 13.629878% across 54 upper-middle-income countries. Assuming the government supports trade openness by reducing tariffs and quotas on exports and imports. Then the government must also reduce corporate income tax to attract FDI into the domestic market. The government should then increase economic growth through pro-foreign investment policies and international trade. After that, the central bank needs to maintain stable and low inflation.

Figure 1: Trade and unemployment in 54 upper-middle-income countries from 1991-2023

If analysed using a graphical approach, it can be seen that international trade has increased over the long term, reflecting globalisation and economic openness. Unemployment has remained relatively stable. However, visually, the relationship between trade and unemployment in this graph is negative, although weak.

4. DISCUSSION

When a country increases exports, there is an increase in demand for goods and services from abroad. Then, to meet export demand, domestic producers will increase production capacity, encouraging labour absorption and directly reducing unemployment. Then, increasing exports to domestic producers will also benefit supporting sectors such as transportation, logistics, financial services, and the raw materials industry. This multiplier effect will create additional jobs in various sectors and reduce unemployment.

After that, due to international trade, countries tend to allocate resources to the most competitive sectors globally. This specialization promotes the development of leading sectors, such as labor-intensive industries in developing countries that employ a large number of workers. Trade openness also forces domestic producers to become more efficient and competitive. Although layoffs may initially occur in uncompetitive sectors, in the long term, companies that survive will become more competitive and expansive, absorbing more workers. Therefore, increasing trade openness through exports and imports can reduce unemployment, which aligns with previous research (Dutt et al., 2009)(Boulhol, 2011)(Felbermayr et al., 2011)(Ranjan, 2012)(Stepanok, 2018)(Alfalih, 2024)(Güven, 2024)(Abdul-Mumuni et al., 2023)(M. M. Ali et al., 2001).

Trade openness usually attracts FDI because market access becomes wider internationally. This FDI will later lead to the establishment of new factories and infrastructure that require local

workers, thereby reducing unemployment. FDI is beneficial as it provides access to technology and managerial practices with more advanced standards in foreign countries, which increases productivity and efficiency, and creates new demand for skilled workers in the local labour market. Therefore, increasing FDI can reduce unemployment, which aligns with previous research (Liu et al., 2022).

When inflation, as measured by the CPI, increases, unemployment rises because the price of goods and services reduces people's purchasing power, and companies' production costs increase. As a result, demand for goods and services decreases, forcing companies to reduce their output and workforce. Then, the economic uncertainty caused by high inflation makes investors and business actors reluctant to expand and refrain from hiring new workers, which in turn increases unemployment. Therefore, low inflation will result in a low unemployment rate, consistent with previous research (Crump et al., 2024)(Bhattarai, 2016)(Cacciatore & Ghironi, 2021)(Kee & Hoon, 2005)(Ferreira de Mendonça, 2009). However, the classical theory of the Phillips curve says otherwise, namely that there is a trade-off between inflation and unemployment, and other researchers also support this trade-off (Moridian et al., 2024)(Lepetit, 2020)(Das, 1997)(Das, 1997)(Karanassou & Sala, 2010). Okun's Law explains the negative relationship between real GDP growth and unemployment rate. Because when real GDP growth indicates the economy is expanding, this expansion encourages increased demand for goods and services, as well as labour needs. So, real GDP growth encourages increased production and investment, which in turn causes increased demand in the labour market, resulting in a decrease in unemployment. The decrease in unemployment due to increased real GDP growth also aligns with previous research (Epifani & Gancia, 2005;Alfalih, 2024).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study shows that trade openness, FDI, and real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth significantly reduce unemployment rates in 54 Upper Middle-Income Countries from 1991 to 2023 in the short and long term. In contrast, inflation has a significant positive impact on unemployment, indicating that price pressures can worsen labour market conditions in the short and long term. Additionally, the unemployment convergence rate of 13.6% per year suggests that developing countries tend to experience a gradual decline in unemployment when macroeconomic and policy conditions are supportive. These findings underscore the importance of economic stability and global trade integration in creating sustainable employment opportunities.

Policy suggestions for the governments of developing countries include expanding trade access by reducing tariffs and non-tariff barriers, allowing the export sector to absorb more workers, especially in labour-intensive sectors. Then the government should reduce corporate income tax and increase the ease of doing business to attract more FDI, which has been proven to impact job creation significantly. Then, the central bank needs to keep inflation low and stable to create a conducive business climate, preventing a decline in labour demand due to rising living costs and production costs. Trade strategies should focus on creating quality jobs through training skilled workers for the development of high-value export-based domestic industries.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://shorturl.at/YZIMI> Table 1: Model unbiasedness test; Table 2: Short-run estimation regression results; Table 3: Long-run estimation regression results; Table 4: Calculating unemployment convergence speed

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

CEM	Common Effect Model
CPI	Consumer Price Index
FD GMM	First Difference Generalised Method of Moments
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
FEM	Fixed Effect Model
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ILO	International Labour Organization
SYS GMM	System Generalised Method of Moments

References

- 1) Abdul-Mumuni, A., Amakye, K., Abukari, A.-L., & Insaiddoo, M. (2023). Modeling trade openness–unemployment nexus in sub-Saharan Africa: the role of asymmetries. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 14(4), 792–805.
- 2) Aleksandravičienė, A., Butkus, M., & Kadisa, T. (2024). Assessing the effect of trade and FDI on growth–unemployment nexus. *Equilibrium. Quarterly Journal of Economics and Economic Policy*, 19(1), 59–91.
- 3) Alfalih, A. A. (2024). The impact of oil prices, foreign direct investment and trade openness on unemployment rates in an oil-exporting country: The case of Saudi Arabia. *Heliyon*, 10(3).
- 4) Ali, M. M., Cecil, H. W., & Knoblett, J. A. (2001). The effects of tax rates and enforcement policies on taxpayer compliance: A study of self-employed taxpayers. *Atlantic Economic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02299137>
- 5) Ali, S., Yusop, Z., Kaliappan, S. R., Chin, L., & Meo, M. S. (2022). Impact of trade openness, human capital, public expenditure and institutional performance on unemployment: evidence from OIC countries. *International Journal of Manpower*, 43(5), 1108–1125.
- 6) Baltagi, B. H., & Baltagi, B. H. (2008). *Econometric analysis of panel data* (Vol. 4). Springer.
- 7) Bhat, M. A., & Beg, M. N. (2023). Revisiting the trade openness–unemployment nexus: an application of the novel JKS panel causality test with static and dynamic panel models. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 50(8), 1889–1907.
- 8) Bhattacharai, K. (2016). Unemployment–inflation trade-offs in OECD countries. *Economic Modelling*, 58, 93–103.
- 9) Boulhol, H. (2011). Unemployment and relative labor market institutions between trading partners. *Journal of International Economics*, 83(1), 83–91.
- 10) Cacciatore, M., & Ghironi, F. (2021). Trade, unemployment, and monetary policy. *Journal of International Economics*, 132, 103488.
- 11) Carnevali, E., & Deleidi, M. (2023). The trade-off between inflation and unemployment in an ‘MMT world’: an open-economy perspective. *European Journal of Economics and Economic Policies*, 20(1), 90–124.
- 12) Crump, R. K., Eusepi, S., Giannoni, M., & Şahin, A. (2024). The unemployment–inflation trade-off revisited: The Phillips curve in COVID times. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 145, 103580.
- 13) Das, S. K. (1997). India’s rupee devaluation, trade balance and unemployment: A producer theory approach. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 8(1), 51–66.

- 14) Demiral, M., Demiral, O., Khoich, A., & Maidyrova, A. (2020). *Empirical links between global value chains, trade and unemployment*.
- 15) Dutt, P., Mitra, D., & Ranjan, P. (2009). International trade and unemployment: Theory and cross-national evidence. *Journal of International Economics*, 78(1), 32–44.
- 16) Epifani, P., & Gancia, G. A. (2005). Trade, migration and regional unemployment. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 35(6), 625–644.
- 17) Felbermayr, G., Prat, J., & Schmerer, H.-J. (2011). Trade and unemployment: What do the data say? *European Economic Review*, 55(6), 741–758.
- 18) Ferreira de Mendonça, H. (2009). Output-inflation and unemployment-inflation trade-offs under inflation targeting: evidence from Brazil. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 36(1), 66–82.
- 19) Gabriel, V. J., Kim, Y. B., Martins, L., & Middleditch, P. (2022). The inflation-unemployment trade-off: empirical considerations and a simple US-Euro Area comparison: Considerações Empíricas e uma Comparação Simples entre EUA e Zona Euro. *Notas Económicas*, 54, 7–26.
- 20) Gonese, D., Sibanda, K., & Ngonisa, P. (2023). Trade openness and unemployment in selected Southern African Development Community (SADC) countries. *Economies*, 11(10), 252.
- 21) Guliyev, H. (2023). Artificial intelligence and unemployment in high-tech developed countries: new insights from dynamic panel data model. *Research in Globalization*, 7, 100140.
- 22) Güven, G. (2024). Urban unemployment, environmental preservation and trade policies in a small open economy with open access renewable resources. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 440, 140912.
- 23) Hasan, R., Mitra, D., Ranjan, P., & Ahsan, R. N. (2012). Trade liberalization and unemployment: Theory and evidence from India. *Journal of Development Economics*, 97(2), 269–280.
- 24) Karanassou, M., & Sala, H. (2010). The US inflation–unemployment trade-off revisited: New evidence for policy-making. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 32(6), 758–777.
- 25) Kee, H. L., & Hoon, H. T. (2005). Trade, capital accumulation and structural unemployment: an empirical study of the Singapore economy. *Journal of Development Economics*, 77(1), 125–152.
- 26) Lepetit, A. (2020). Asymmetric unemployment fluctuations and monetary policy trade-offs. *Review of Economic Dynamics*, 36, 29–45.
- 27) Liu, Z., Ngo, T. Q., Saydaliev, H. B., He, H., & Ali, S. (2022). How do trade openness, public expenditure and institutional performance affect unemployment in OIC countries? Evidence from the DCCE approach. *Economic Systems*, 46(4), 101023.
- 28) Moridian, A., Radulescu, M., Usman, M., Mahdavian, S. M. R., Hagi, A., & Serbanescu, L. (2024). Unemployment rate and its relationship with government size, trade, inflation, urbanization, and economic growth in Romania. *Heliyon*.
- 29) Ranjan, P. (2012). Trade liberalization, unemployment, and inequality with endogenous job destruction. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 23, 16–29.
- 30) Ribba, A. (2022). Monetary policy shocks in open economies and the inflation unemployment trade-off: The case of the Euro Area. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(4), 146.
- 31) Roodman, D. (2009). A note on the theme of too many instruments. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 71(1), 135–158.
- 32) Stepanok, I. (2018). A North–South model of trade with search unemployment. *European Economic Review*, 101, 546–566.